

Formal weaknesses of some definitions of roughness, and a solution proposal

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Abstract— We have analyzed from a formal point of view two definitions of roughness. Both are applicable only for elevations modeled through a DEM. One (named α) states that roughness is computed as the standard deviation of the slope at the 9 grid points of a 3x3 window. Another similar one (named β), computes the same over a detrended version of the elevation surface. As defined, we prove that both roughness values vanish at the limit of the cell size going down to zero, irrespective of any other characteristic of the terrain. Despite both metrics attempt to compute a property of the topographical surface through the use of a regular sample of elevations (i.e. DEM) we can show that the value is still a function of the cell size. Thus, a seemingly intrinsic property of the topographic surface is dependent of one arbitrary characteristic of the sample: the DEM cell size. Through a cumbersome but otherwise straightforward formal manipulation we can prove that the squared standard deviation of the slope over a 3x3 window is directly proportional to the cell size h raised to a power 1 or 2. If we consider instead the slightly modified definition β where the surface is first detrended, then the power is always 2. The proposed adjusted definition of roughness requires using the standard deviation of the detrended slope over a 3x3 window divided by the squared cell size h . We will show the relationship of such magnitude to the set of partial derivatives of the topographic surface, thus offering a mathematical counterpart of the so defined roughness. In addition, a procedure to estimate its uncertainty under the assumption that the elevation values are error free is also provided.

I. INTRODUCTION

The DEMIX initiative [1] conducted a comparison exercise between global DEM of 1 arc second resolution. Among other criteria, it was proposed to compare the accuracy of the roughness obtained from the candidate vs. what is deemed as a reference value. Since the reference could be computed from a local DEM of higher resolution, it was questioned if the

computation should be carried out at high resolution and later coarsened, or first coarsened and then computed. It was argued that the roughness derived from high resolution DEM was systematically different from the candidate one. Also, no cue about its accuracy was offered, since as defined the roughness is not easily measurable in the field. According to [2] there are a number of possible definitions for roughness. Following some authors, ([3], [4]) and within DEMIX interim report [5], roughness was defined for every grid point in terms of the standard deviation of the slope computed at the points of a 3x3 window centered in the point. Such definition (denoted hereinafter as α) was used throughout this paper despite that, according to [6], the final chosen window for DEMIX was 7x7. If we denote as S_i , $i=\{1,2,\dots,9\}$ the slope value computed at the i -th point, the mean slope M and the roughness R will be

$$M = \frac{1}{9} \sum_1^9 S_i; R = \sqrt{\frac{1}{8} \sum_1^9 (S_i - M)^2} \quad (1)$$

For convenience we will work with the squared roughness R^2 hereinafter. It is clear that, provided a 3x3 window is used to compute the slope, all points of the 5x5 window will be involved in the computation of R^2 (see Fig. 1).

Irrespective of the windows size within DEMIX most of the comparison was done resorting to an independent reference dataset. In order to declare that some value could be considered as a reference one, we should be able to confirm that its accuracy is significantly better than the value under analysis. That was offered at [7] for the computation of the slope and aspect. Unlike slope, for roughness we have not resorted to a mathematical definition but just to the computation procedure. So, our first goal will be to find an expression showing the relationship between the roughness and the local properties of the topographical surface at point 1. To the best of our knowledge this has never been done before. Once we have such relationship, we will be able to consider similar tricks as used by [7] in order to estimate

its uncertainty. The formulae are strictly valid only for the stated roughness definition, but illustrate the procedure for other ones.

Figure 1. 3x3 (light blue) and 5x5 (light blue and yellow) computation window. Roughness is to be defined at point 1, but definitions α and β involve all points in the 5x5 window (from [7])

In this paper we will not discuss the representativeness of so defined roughness for the intended purpose neither its interpretability. We will just argue around some basic formal properties, using as a starting point not a mathematical but an algorithmic definition. Some authors even questioned the status of the roughness as a significant parameter. For example, [8] states that it is not a morphometric variable. We refer the reader to traditional references as [9] for further analysis.

We will show that both considered definitions of roughness could not describe an intrinsic property of the terrain surface. In particular, both are dependent on the cell size h and vanish when h goes down to zero. If we remove the dependency w.r.t. h , then different grids will have different roughness as now, but the dependence with h will be removed. The roughness will be a function of the point value of some partial derivatives. For finite h they will be just an estimate of the limit value, which does not automatically goes down to 0.0 everywhere if h decreases. We will suggest a slight modification that addresses or solves the issue. With such modification an uncertainty estimate could be formally derived, which in turn could be used to compute roughness reference values from other sources.

II. WHAT IS INDEED ESTIMATED

Computing the slope of points of a 3x3 window using a 3x3 rule spans over a 5x5 window. All the elevation values at the nodes of the 5x5 window can be expressed in terms of the Taylor expansion of the topographical surface function around the point 1 and the cell size (Δ_x, Δ_y) . It is immediate that all the slope values, derived from them will also be a function of the same variables. As a conclusion, the so-defined roughness will also be a function of the partial derivatives at point 1, as well as the cell size.

A. Establishing the relationship between roughness and partial derivatives for the first definition

There is no mathematical definition of the roughness at hand but just a computation algorithm. The procedure to compute the squared roughness R^2 is as follows:

1. For every point i , $i=\{1,\dots,9\}$ compute the slope S_i using (for example) the Evans-Young formula [10]
2. Compute M , the mean slope S_i , $i=\{1,\dots,9\}$
3. Compute the squared standard deviation of the slope S_i , $i=\{1,\dots,9\}$

The exact expression for the roughness in terms of point value elevation is very long, but otherwise tractable. It can be shown that it differs depending if the local slope vanishes or not. If we collect all the terms and use just the partial derivatives at point 1 we obtain (Eq. 2):

$$R^2 = \begin{cases} \frac{3}{4} \left[\frac{P_x^2 (f_x f_{xx} + f_y f_{yy})^2 + P_y^2 (f_y f_{yy} + f_x f_{xx})^2}{f_x^2 + f_y^2} \right] h + O(h^3) & \text{if } f_x^2 + f_y^2 \neq 0 \\ \left\{ -\frac{1}{9} [(P+Q)(UP_x + VP_y) + UVP_x P_y + PQ] + \frac{7}{24} (P^2 + Q^2) \right\} h^2 + O(h^3) & \text{if } f_x^2 + f_y^2 = 0 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

being

$$U = \sqrt{f_{xx}^2 + f_{yy}^2}; V = \sqrt{f_{yy}^2 + f_{xx}^2}; W = f_{xy} (f_{xx} + f_{yy}) \\ P = \sqrt{U^2 P_x^2 - 2WP_y P_x + V^2 P_y^2}; Q = \sqrt{U^2 P_x^2 + 2WP_y P_x + V^2 P_y^2} \quad (3) \\ h = \max(\Delta_x, \Delta_y); P_x = \Delta_x/h; P_y = \Delta_y/h$$

Some comments regarding this expression:

- The partial derivatives are a property of the topographic surface function, while h , P_x and P_y are a property of its sampling strategy (i.e. the DEM)
- Ideally, the roughness value should be invariant after rotation of the reference frame [11].
- If we neglect the numerical importance of P_x and P_y (both will be 1.0 if the grid is square), in the general case the squared roughness can be interpreted as the product of a property of the terrain and the grid size h . The key conclusion is that its value will go down to zero when h goes to zero, irrespective of the characteristics of the terrain.
- If the center point has zero slope the limit value for the roughness is also zero but now at least quadratic with h .
- As defined, the first terms of the Taylor expansion of the squared roughness are a function of the first and second order derivatives, not involving higher order ones.

In order to make the squared roughness α independent on the DEM design, in the general case its value should be divided by the largest grid dimension h raised to the power 1 or 2 depending on the local slope. The fact that the exponent is not constant is an issue which complicates further manipulations [2]. In any case, we uncovered the limit value for the so-defined roughness in terms of local partial derivatives, which is one main result of this paper.

B. Establishing the relationship between roughness and partial derivatives for the β definition

It is interesting to notice that some authors proposed to compute the roughness using not the DEM elevations but its difference with those of a best fit plane [12]. Such plane through point 1 will be selected with the same exact slope as the topographical surface. Its difference will have, by consequence, a zero slope in the center, leading to the particular case already studied. Despite not very popular in the literature, such detrended surface option has been informally considered at earlier stages within DEMIX. To the best of our knowledge such definition (named β hereinafter) has never been published. To be strict the exact slope at point 1 is not known in advance. Because a 5x5 window is already involved, it is fit to use a better schema for estimating it than the lower order one due to Evans-Young [10].

It has been shown [7] that with a 5x5 window the first partial derivatives p and q can be computed with 4th order accuracy using the schema proposed by [13]. Using our point numbering definition, the formula for each component of the first partial derivative is

$$p = \frac{1}{420h} \{44(f_{13} - f_{11} + f_{19} - f_{21}) + 31[f_{10} - f_{14} + f_{22} - f_{18} + 2(f_4 - f_2 + f_6 - f_8)] + 17[f_{16} - f_{24} + 4(f_5 - f_9)] + 5(f_{15} - f_{25} + f_{17} - f_{23})\} + h^4 \left(\frac{1}{30} f_{xxxx} + \frac{17}{30} f_{xyyy} + \frac{3}{35} f_{yyyy} \right) + O(h^6) \quad (4)$$

$$q = \frac{1}{420h} \{44(f_{25} - f_{23} + f_{15} - f_{17}) + 31[f_{22} - f_{10} + f_{18} - f_{14} + 2(f_2 - f_8 + f_4 - f_6)] + 17[f_{12} - f_{20} + 4(f_3 - f_7)] + 5(f_{11} - f_{21} + f_{13} - f_{19})\} + h^4 \left(\frac{1}{30} f_{yyyy} + \frac{17}{30} f_{xyyy} + \frac{3}{35} f_{xxxx} \right) + O(h^6) \quad (5)$$

where f_i stands for the elevation at the i -th point (following Fig. 1) and the suffix x and y denote partial derivatives of the surface. After a rather involved formal manipulation, the squared roughness from the detrended surface can be presented as a multiple of the grid size squared, being the multiple a function of the second order derivatives. The particular case already considered of zero slope at point 1 is still valid, provided the fourth order estimate due to [13] for the 5x5 window is used for detrending. This result could not be anticipated, and if we use instead a lower order estimate it can be different.

$$\frac{R_{\text{det}}^2}{h^2} = \frac{7}{24}(P^2 + U^2) - \frac{1}{9}[(P+Q)(UP_x + VP_y) + UVP_x P_y + PQ] + O(h) \quad (6)$$

Regarding this second expression, the limit for small h links the scaled squared roughness from the detrended surface to a rather convoluted function of the second derivatives of the topographic surface. No higher order derivatives are involved in such limit value. We can conclude that the traditional roughness divided by the cell size h will now have a limit when it goes to zero. Let's denote as r_h^2 the detrended scaled squared roughness.

C. Estimating the uncertainty of the roughness value

If the β definition is adopted, then the detrended scaled squared roughness can be computed with second order accuracy in general, irrespective of the local slope. In both definitions we are interested in estimating an uncertainty value. We will assume that the elevations are without error, and the only source of uncertainty is due to the finite cell size h . Given that the exponent is known, one possibility to estimate an uncertainty value is to use the Richardson Extrapolation [14] as [7] did. The approach is simple but has two weaknesses. First, for the α definition the order might vary between 1 and 2. Second, and more important, it mixes estimates with different scales. An alternative option (not fully researched yet) is to compute the slope at the 9 points but using for each a 5x5 window. The overall window will be thus 7x7. The higher order formulae for slope will produce a higher order estimate of roughness, even using the β definition. With two estimates of the same roughness value each with different order we can compute its uncertainty as the absolute value of its difference. This alternative was presented also in [7] for the slope and aspect. The main advantage w.r.t. the Richardson Extrapolation option is that it only involves a grid of cell size h , thus assuring that scale is fully comparable between high and low order estimates. The computational effort is anyway modest.

The mixing of two different order estimates will work properly either for α or β roughness definition. On the other hand, the Richardson Extrapolation option does not hold for the α definition because the remainder has different power of h depending whether the local slope vanishes or not.

III. DISCUSSION

- We have found the analytical, exact expression, relating roughness definitions α and β to local partial derivatives.
- The β definition leads to a limit value that only involves second order derivatives of the topographic surface. Unlike the α definition, its order is also constant.
- We offer two different uncertainty estimates. One might be poisoned with scale issues, because for the Richardson extrapolation we use terms from cell size h and $2h$. This is a problem. The second one uses the higher order formula

by [13] involving a local 5x5 window to compute the slope. Following this workaround the cell size will be always h , so no scale issues will affect the estimate. For the sake of completeness in future works we should establish the order of the leading term of the Taylor expansion, which certainly will be larger than 2.

- Comparable roughness values are important only while dealing with DEMs of different cell size. Within DEMIX all of them were 1” DEMs (same h) so the roughness estimate with one DEM is indeed comparable with the one from another. However, the reference values used to measure the accuracy are questionable.
- Obtaining reference values for roughness are not easy feat. High resolution datasets can produce estimates for a given h through a moving window. The resulting high resolution dataset of h -resolution roughness values could then safely be processed, and an uncertainty value could be derived provided we have a Taylor expansion analysis like the one offered here. Merely using higher accuracy elevations need not to be enough in order to satisfy the requirements to produce a suitable reference roughness dataset.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

- We have found the analytical, exact expression, relating two different definitions of roughness (α and β) to local partial derivatives and the cell size h .
- It has been shown that the limit value of the roughness for the β definition only involves second order derivatives.
- Future works might complete the analysis of uncertainty estimates which properly deal with scale issues. However, the solution will not be complete unless we can consider the effect of the uncertain elevations. Such activity has been done for the case of elevation and for the case of slope (but still unpublished) and needs to be developed from scratch in the case of roughness.
- In order to gather a roughness reference value, the rule is “compute first, resample later”, but using a DEM of sufficiently higher resolution.
- Other algorithmic definitions of roughness (standard deviation of the elevation over a 3x3 window, for example) are waiting for a detailed analysis as illustrated here producing its mathematical counterpart.

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